

**Süni intellekt: nəzəriyyədən prktikaya, beynəlxalq konfrans,
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**Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı MobileNet Modelleri ile Beton Çatlaklarının Erken
Tespiti ve Güvenlik**

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Özet

Beton yapıların güvenliği ve dayanıklılığı açısından, çatlakların erken tespit edilmesi büyük önem taşımaktadır, zira bu çatlaklar zamanında müdahale edilmediğinde ciddi yapısal hasarlara yol açabilir. Bu bağlamda, çatlakların hızlı ve doğru bir şekilde saptanması, yapısal hasar değerlendirmelerinin etkinliğini artırmak için kritik bir rol oynar. Bu çalışmada, beton yüzeylerdeki çatlakların tespiti amacıyla derin öğrenme tabanlı MobileNetV2 ve MobileNetV3 mimarileri kullanılmıştır. MobileNet mimarileri, hafif yapıları ve yüksek verimlilikleri sayesinde, kısıtlı kaynaklara sahip ortamlarda dahi yüksek performans sunarken, tespit doğruluğundan ödün vermemeleri nedeniyle tercih edilmiştir. Çalışmada kullanılan görüntü verileri, Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi'nin (ODTÜ) 20.000 negatif ve 20.000 pozitif örnekten oluşan halka açık bir veri setinden elde edilmiştir. Bu modellerin kullanımı, beton yüzeylerdeki çatlakların tespitinde doğruluğu ve verimliliği artırmayı hedefleyerek, erken hasar değerlendirmesi ve bakım planlaması için etkili bir araç sunmayı amaçlamaktadır. Deneysel sonuçlar, derin öğrenme yöntemlerinin ve özellikle MobileNet ağlarının bu alanda yüksek başarı ve etkinlikte teşhis sağlayabildiğini ortaya koymuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler : Derin öğrenme, Evrimsel sinir ağları, Çatlak tespiti

Abstract

The early detection of cracks is crucial for ensuring the safety and durability of concrete structures, as these cracks can lead to significant structural damage if not addressed promptly. In this context, the rapid and accurate identification of cracks plays a vital role in enhancing the effectiveness of structural damage assessments. This study employs deep learning-based MobileNetV2 and MobileNetV3 architectures to detect cracks on concrete surfaces. These MobileNet architectures were chosen for their lightweight design and high efficiency, which allow for high performance even in resource-constrained environments without sacrificing detection accuracy. The image data used in the study was sourced from a publicly available dataset provided by Middle East Technical University (METU), consisting of 20,000 negative and 20,000 positive samples. The use of these models aims to improve the accuracy and efficiency of crack detection on concrete surfaces, providing a robust tool for early damage assessment and maintenance planning. Experimental results demonstrate that deep learning methods, particularly MobileNet networks, are highly effective and successful in this field of diagnosis.

Keywords : Deep learning, convolutional neural networks, crack detection

1. Introduction

Cracks on concrete surfaces can occur gradually or as a result of natural disasters such as earthquakes. It is critical to recognize these cracks quickly and precisely in order to reduce both material and emotional losses. Regular and thorough inspections are required to quickly locate and repair cracks, ensuring the durability and protection of concrete surfaces. Crack detection on a regular basis is critical for maintaining building structural integrity because these cracks frequently indicate future damage. This detection approach helps to prevent serious damage in aging structures, which require frequent maintenance [1, 2]. Visual inspections are commonly used to evaluate the condition of non-destructive constructions [3]. However, this method is tedious and time-consuming, needing trained inspectors to manually evaluate visuals. The reliance on human expertise emphasizes the urgent need to automate and improve visual assessment procedures.

Over time, researchers developed algorithms to automatically detect flaws in concrete surfaces. The introduction of deep learning in computer vision has demonstrated extraordinary potential for handling classification, detection, and recognition problems [4]. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) include more layers and parameters than traditional machine learning algorithms [5]. DNNs excel in detecting objects at all levels, from the image to the pixel, allowing each pixel to be identified as a component of the target object [6]. Current research focuses on improving the accuracy of DNNs, particularly for fracture identification in individual images [4-6]. Despite their advantages, these systems' output is limited to specific areas represented by individual photographs. A system for correctly and efficiently visualizing large-scale crack detection has yet to be widely used in the field.

In crack detection research, CNN architectures are widely used and recommended. The OLeNet model was developed by a study of 40,000 picture data points. The OLeNet model was validated using a shallow layer stack, with a maximum accuracy of 99.8% [7]. Recently, alongside deep CNN architectures, the Mask R-CNN and Faster R-CNN architectures are also under investigation for their potential contributions to crack detection studies.

The Mask R-CNN architecture targets cost reduction by generating masks corresponding to significant features on cracked surfaces [8]. Furthermore, Faster R-CNN is employed to observe weather conditions. Various studies focusing on crack detection have been conducted. In one such study, images with a resolution of 4128 x 2322 were utilized, and crack detection analyses were conducted by altering shooting conditions on a concrete road [9]. Comparing the Faster R-CNN and Mask R-CNN architectures, it's noted that the Mask R-CNN architecture exhibits superior performance in crack detection [10]. Joshi et al. (2022) proposed a deep learning strategy for autonomously recognizing, categorizing, and segmenting surface cracks. They observed the model's ability to identify even hairline flaws, especially under specific lighting conditions [11]. Han et al. (2022) used the cutting-edge Mask R-CNN method to accurately recognize and locate desiccation cracks in clayey soil [12]. Feng et al. (2017) focused on damage detection inside Hydro-Junction Infrastructure [13]. In a separate investigation, a lightweight convolutional neural network was utilized to detect tunnel cracks in a dataset comprising 1218 images. The Lightweight Convolutional Neural Network was evaluated against SegNet, U-Net, and DeepCrack, demonstrating faster processing speeds [14]. Sermet and Pascal mobilenet conducted a study that found concrete crack detection with over 90% accuracy with the help of deep learning architectures [15].

The aim of this study is to evaluate and compare Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) models for the detection of cracks on concrete surfaces using deep learning methods. Cracks formed in concrete

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structures are of great importance for the early detection of structural damage. Therefore, the study aimed to detect cracks on concrete surfaces quickly and successfully using different CNN architectures. In addition, by analyzing the performances of the deep and lightweight CNN models based on accuracy, precision, sensitivity and F1-score, it was investigated whether high accuracy could be achieved with fewer parameters. In conclusion, this study evaluates the effectiveness of deep learning models in concrete crack detection, while also examining the usefulness of lightweight models that require less resources.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 CNN architecture

Despite its development starting in the 1980s, CNN architecture didn't gain prominence in the field of machine learning until 2012, coinciding with the advent of large datasets. CNNs are adept at extracting object features from images and distinguishing between them. This architecture comprises multiple layers, forming a mathematical structure [16]. Central to CNNs is the convolution process, a mathematical operation that generates a new function representing the modification of one shape by another [17]. A typical CNN includes an input layer, an output layer, and various intermediary layers responsible for mathematical operations, primarily convolutions [18]. In a convolutional neural network, the convolutional layer acquires essential features through the utilization of a multi-layer kernel, while the fully connected layers learn from these feature [19].

2.2 Dataset

The dataset comprises images depicting concrete with cracks, sourced from different buildings within the METU Campus [20]. It is categorized into negative and positive crack images for classification purposes. Each category contains 20,000 images, totaling 40,000 images, all sized 227 x 227 pixels with RGB channels. These images stem from 458 high-resolution images (4032x3024 pixels) using the technique outlined by Zhang et al. (2016) [21]. These high-resolution images vary in surface texture and lighting conditions. No data augmentation techniques such as random rotation or flipping were utilized. In Figure 1, several images are given for cracked and non-cracked concrete surfaces for the METU dataset.

Figure 1. Some sample images from METU dataset

Table 1 illustrates how the images from the METU dataset were utilized for training, validation, and testing of the models.

Table 1. Dataset pre-processing details

Class	Input size	Total Images (%100)	Train (%70)	Validation (%15)	Test (%15)
Crack	224x224	20000	14000	3000	3000
Non-crack	224x224	20000	14000	3000	3000
Total	224x224	40000	28000	6000	6000

Table 1 explains how the images from the METU dataset were processed and distributed across different stages of model development. The dataset contains 40,000 images, equally divided between crack and non-crack categories, with each class having 20,000 images. To keep everything consistent, all the images were resized to 224x224 pixels, ensuring uniform input for the models. For training, 70 percent of the dataset, which means 14,000 images from each class, was used to help the models learn patterns and features effectively. Another 15 percent, or 3,000 images per class, was set aside for validation. This validation step was essential in fine-tuning the models, allowing adjustments to be made to prevent overfitting and ensure they could generalize well to new data. The final 15 percent of the dataset, again 3,000 images per class, was used for testing, providing an opportunity to assess how well the models performed on completely unseen images. By carefully organizing the dataset this way, the models were able to train, validate, and test in a balanced and systematic manner, resulting in a more reliable and accurate performance for detecting concrete cracks.

2.3 MobileNet Architectures

MobileNet models are progressively being developed using more efficient components. MobileNetV1 [22] proposed depthwise separable convolutions as a more efficient replacement for standard convolution layers. These convolutions break down traditional convolutions by isolating the spatial filtering process from feature extraction. Depthwise separable convolutions consist of two layers: a lightweight depthwise convolution that handles spatial filtering and a more computationally intensive 1x1 pointwise convolution for feature generation.

MobileNetV2 [23] introduced the linear bottleneck and inverted residual architecture to develop more efficient layer structures by taking advantage of the problem's low-rank nature. As illustrated in Figure 3, this architecture consists of a 1x1 expansion convolution, followed by depthwise convolutions, and a 1x1 projection layer. A residual connection is used only when the input and output have the same number of channels. This design expands into a higher-dimensional feature space internally to enhance the expressive power of nonlinear transformations per channel, while keeping a compact representation at the input and output.

MobileNetV3[24] is a smart, efficient deep learning model crafted to work seamlessly on devices with limited power, like smartphones and embedded systems. Building on the success of its predecessor, MobileNetV2, Google fine-tuned MobileNetV3 using advanced technologies like AutoML and Neural Architecture Search to ensure it delivers both speed and efficiency. What really sets it apart are features like Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) blocks and the hard-swish activation function, which give it a significant performance boost. MobileNetV3 comes in two versions: the Large model, perfect for tasks that demand high accuracy, and the Small model, tailored for situations where saving resources is a

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priority. This makes it a practical and powerful tool, ideal for everyday applications like image recognition and object detection on commonly used devices.

3. Results

3.1. Experimental Design

Deep learning algorithms rely heavily on GPU-based graphics cards because they allow for faster processing of large datasets by taking advantage of parallel computing. NVIDIA's CUDA architecture is a go-to choice for training these models. In this study, the hardware setup featured a powerful combination: a Linux-based Ubuntu 22.04 system, an NVIDIA RTX 2080TI graphics card with 11 GB of GDDR6 memory and 4352 CUDA cores, an Intel Core i9 9900X processor with 10 cores running at 3.50 GHz, and 32 GB of DDR4 RAM. PyTorch was chosen as the deep learning framework, with Python used as the programming language to tie everything together, ensuring a smooth and efficient training process.

3.2. Experimental Results

In this section, the statistical results and evaluations of the success of MobileNet deep learning models on the METU dataset are discussed. The METU dataset consists of two main classes, cracked and uncracked. As a result of the analysis, the experimental results for MobileNetv2 and MobileNetv3 deep learning models are shown in Table-2.

Table 2. Experimental results of the MobileNet variants on METU dataset

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
MobileNetv2-050	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992
MobileNetv2-100	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992
MobileNetv2-140	0.9997	0.9997	0.9997	0.9997
MobileNetv3-small-075	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995
MobileNetv3-small-100	0.9993	0.9993	0.9993	0.9993
MobileNetv3-large-075	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995
MobileNetv3-large-100	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992	0.9992

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In this study, we explored how different MobileNet models performed on the METU dataset, focusing on key metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The results were incredibly close across the board, but there are some important distinctions between the MobileNetV2 and MobileNetV3 models that are worth highlighting. Both the MobileNetV2-050 and MobileNetV2-100 models delivered identical results, with 99.92% across all metrics—impressive consistency. However, the MobileNetV2-140 model took things up a notch, reaching an outstanding accuracy of 99.97%. This slight improvement can be traced back to its deeper structure and larger number of parameters, allowing it to better handle the scale of the dataset. Models like the MobileNetV2-140, with their added complexity, tend to excel when applied to larger datasets.

The MobileNetV3 models showed some interesting nuances. The MobileNetV3-Small-075 model achieved a 99.95% accuracy, slightly outperforming the MobileNetV3-Small-100, which scored 99.93%. These small but notable differences demonstrate how adjustments to the model's scale can influence its performance. When looking at the MobileNetV3-Large models, the MobileNetV3-Large-075 also stood out with a 99.95% accuracy, whereas the MobileNetV3-Large-100 matched the MobileNetV2 models at 99.92%. This shows that simply increasing a model's size or adding more parameters doesn't always guarantee higher accuracy—what matters more is how well the model is tailored to the specific task. The clear standout here is the MobileNetV2-140, with its stellar 99.97% accuracy, making it the best-performing model in this study. Its deep architecture and large parameter set were particularly well-suited to the METU dataset. However, the MobileNetV3-Small-075 and MobileNetV3-Large-075 models also performed exceptionally well, each with a 99.95% accuracy. This highlights the impressive efficiency of the MobileNetV3 architecture, proving that it can achieve high performance even with lower resource consumption.

All MobileNet models demonstrated exceptional accuracy, with each model surpassing 99%. Among them, the MobileNetV2-140 emerged as the top performer, delivering the highest accuracy at 99.97%, showcasing its ability to handle more complex tasks with its deeper architecture and increased parameter count. The MobileNetV3 models, particularly the Small-075 and Large-075 variants, also performed remarkably well with 99.95% accuracy, proving that even with lower resource consumption, these models can still achieve competitive results. This makes the MobileNetV3 variants ideal for scenarios where resource efficiency is a priority without sacrificing too much in terms of accuracy. Figure 2 presents the confusion matrix for the MobileNetV2-140 model, which achieved the highest accuracy, showcasing its performance across different classes.

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Figure 2. Confusion matrix for mobileNetv2-140

As shown in Figure 2, the TP values for both crack and non-crack are notably high. The crack class has 3000 true positives with only 2 false positives, while the non-crack class has 2998 true positives with just 2 false negatives. This demonstrates the model's strong performance, even at the class level.

4. Discussion

The experimental results clearly show how effective the MobileNet models are, particularly the MobileNetV2 140 variant, in detecting concrete cracks using the METU dataset. In this study, different MobileNet versions were compared based on key metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Remarkably, all models performed exceptionally well, with accuracy rates exceeding 99 percent. Among them, MobileNetV2 140 stood out with an impressive 99.97 percent accuracy. This highlights the model's superior performance, thanks to its deeper structure and higher number of parameters. Its ability to manage larger datasets and handle complex tasks is especially noticeable in situations where precision is of utmost importance. When looking at the MobileNetV2 and MobileNetV3 variants, the MobileNetV3 models, particularly the small 075 and large 075 versions, also showed high accuracy levels, reaching 99.95 percent. While the MobileNetV2 140 model delivers the best overall performance, the MobileNetV3 variants offer a great balance between accuracy and resource efficiency. This suggests that MobileNetV3's design is powerful, providing high performance even in settings where resources are limited, making it an excellent option for fast and efficient crack detection without sacrificing much in terms of accuracy. Another significant finding, seen in the confusion matrix in Figure 3, is the high number of true positives for both the crack and non-crack classes. The model successfully detected 3000 true positives in the crack class and 2998 in the non-crack class, with only 2 false positives and 2 false negatives. This underlines the precision and reliability of the MobileNetV2 140 model in accurately classifying cracks across different categories.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights how effective and accurate MobileNet models are in detecting cracks in concrete, with the MobileNetV2 140 model performing particularly well. Achieving an impressive accuracy of 99.97 percent, it proves to be an excellent tool for early damage detection and maintenance planning in concrete structures. Its deeper architecture allows it to excel in handling complex tasks, making it a standout in the research. The MobileNetV3 variants, particularly the small 075 and large 075 models, also demonstrate strong results. They strike a perfect balance between accuracy and resource efficiency, making them ideal for applications where both precision and performance are critical, yet resources may be limited. These findings confirm the effectiveness of deep learning models like MobileNet for automated crack detection. They offer a reliable and efficient way to maintain the structural integrity of concrete across various environments, making them invaluable for modern construction and infrastructure management.

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